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Grade 11 Senior High School Students' Level of Anxiety in Public Speaking: Causes and Strategies

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Abstract

In the age of globalization, learning the English language in Senior High School is essential. One way of learning the English language is through speaking activities. However, there are still students who are anxious whenever they engage in a speaking activity. Hence, this study aims to measure the speaking anxiety level of Grade 11 students and to determine its causes as well as to provide strategies to overcome speech anxiety. This study used a descriptive-comparative research design. The number of Grade 11 senior high school respondents was determined using purposive random sampling. James McCroskey's Personal Report on Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA) was used in order to determine the student's level of anxiety in public speaking. The results showed that the respondents had a moderately high level of anxiety. Also, variables such as strand, school graduated from, and socioeconomic status have no significant difference in their speech anxiety. Then, the sex of the respondents was found to have no significant difference with the respondents' speech anxiety. Furthermore, it was found that fear of negative evaluation is the most common reason why students experience speech anxiety. Meanwhile, preparation is the most effective way to use as a strategy in coping with speech anxiety. Therefore, this study has pedagogical implications for teaching and learning speaking.

Keywords: *PRPSA, speech anxiety, causes of anxiety, English language, strategies*

Introduction

The K-12 Basic Education Curriculum offers Oral Communication in Context as one of the core subjects in the Senior High School curriculum. This subject aims to develop the listening and speaking skills of the students as well as the strategies for effective communication in various situations. Hence, English is the primary language used in studying this core subject.

At the same time, it provides skills for effective delivery such as communicative competence which can be defined as the capacity to freely communicate or deliver ideas, thoughts, and feelings to an audience (Northwest Augmentative Communication Society, 2021). According to Dr. Janice Light (1989), people who use augmentative/alternative communication (ACC) learn and combine knowledge, judgment, and skills in four connected areas: linguistic, strategic, socio-linguistic, and discourse. According to Seni (2016), linguistic or grammar Competence can be associated with the aspect of mastery of the language code. Socio-linguistic Competence requires the speaker to be knowledgeable of the social context in which a language is used. The context depends on elements including the participants' standing, the information they exchange, and the goals of interaction, as well as customs or rules about it. Discourse Competence, focuses on the proficiency at combining grammatical forms and means to produce a coherent speech performance. And lastly Strategic Competence, is made up of both verbal and non-verbal communication strategies for communication that might be employed to make up for breakdowns due to restrictive circumstances in real conversation and to improve the speech's delivery.

Learning the English language in Senior High School is essential and should be taken seriously. The world is now more interconnected than ever. The English language is no longer the language of English native speakers living in America or United Kingdom, but it is a lingua franca of the world (Abbasi et. al., 2019). Because of this, the growing use of English as an international language is growing faster. Filipinos communicate and understand English in their daily lives. Despite the fact that the English language has been taught from primary to tertiary levels of education, some of the students still find English challenging to learn and difficult to master, especially when it comes to speaking.

Despite living in a country where English is considered a Second Language, Filipinos still get anxious when speaking in public. According to Del Villar (2010), despite Filipino students having an innate knowledge of what causes their public speaking anxiety, even identifying academic pressure is identified as a number one factor. Students could still not be able to control or find proper techniques to control their anxieties. This leads to at least 69.11% of the respondents being identified as High Level of Anxiety. Even after the pandemic, the result still remained the same, in a study conducted by Ong & Zambas (2021), the students who were respondents to the study obtained a moderate and high anxiety level in terms of public speaking anxiety. Another factor that may affect students' level of anxiety may be their socio-economic status. According to PISA (Program for International Student Assessment), "socio-economically advantaged students usually perform better in PISA than disadvantaged students, but the gap in reading performance related to socio-economic status varies considerably across countries". In 2022, The Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries globally in the student assessment conducted by the OECD (The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) for 15-year-old learners. One of the possible reasons for this may be because Filipino students have a low socioeconomic status, not having enough resources to acquire better learning materials or schooling.

Through these findings it can be said that students' developing speaking skills are always regarded as complex and challenging,

requiring a great deal of effort to maintain (Kashinathan & Aziz, 2021). With this, Filipinos experience public speaking anxiety even at a young age. It can be experienced anywhere at any point in life or profession. Accordingly, public speaking anxiety can also be experienced in the school environment. In Oral Communication in Context (OralCom) subject, various public speaking activities are conducted such as delivering impromptu, extemporaneous, manuscript, and memorized speeches which could trigger speech anxiety. Due to these activities present in the subject, there might be a chance for Grade 11 students anxious about public speeches given that the OralCom subject has these activities, with these instances this became the basis for the study to be conducted at Saint Mary's University, as a form of help for the students.

Public Speaking

Public speaking is a process, an act, and an art of making a speech before an audience (Nikitina, 2011). It is delivering speeches in front of an audience to persuade, inform, or entertain an audience. In delivering these speeches in public, learners are expected to acquire English vocabulary-building skills to maximize their learning capabilities through speaking (Leaño et al., 2019).

Moreover, according to Ezeukwu (2000), public communication or speaking is a third concentric setting of face-to-face communication in which one person speaks while a considerable number of other people listen. This means that a person speaking in front of an audience can vary. Their audience can be a couple of people, strangers, or a class full of students such as themselves.

According to Chen (2022), there are a lot of speeches that can be executed. But mainly, it can be categorized into four: Ceremonial Speaking, Demonstrative Speaking, Informative Speaking, and Persuasive Speaking. Ceremonial Speaking can be defined as the delivery of a speech during an event. An example is an office party, graduations, and many more. This type of speech can be seen as a bit problematic, especially for those who do not like to speak in front of a big crowd, this can be attributed to stage fright. According to Adena et al. (2020), stage fright can lead to a presenter being in their worst state to perform on stage which highly affects their performances, especially for those in an academic setting. The next type of speaking is Demonstrative Speaking, which can be simply defined as explaining how to do something. One of the main examples of this type of speaking activity in a school setting is presentations. According to Grieve et al. (2020), students feel a lot of fear in oral speaking presentations such as recitations or even class presentations. The third type is Informative speaking, it is the act of informing a large crowd in the form of an individual into a larger group. Similar to the two previous types of speaking types this could be a hybrid version of both types. Is similar to a ceremonial where one speaks into a big crowd and a demonstrative where you inform. Lastly, Persuasive speaking is an idea of persuading your audience into an idea or your own viewpoint. The most common type of this speaking type is a persuasive speech, debates, or campaign speeches.

Public speaking, then, plays an important part in the context of Philippine Education. Hence, it is also important to know what can be done to make students learn more about what makes them anxious when public speaking.'

Public Speaking Anxiety

The feeling of fear, becoming anxious when performing or speaking, or if one becomes the center of attention impedes the students from performing effectively in public speaking activities. According to Rachman and Rachman (2020), anxiety is a tense unsettling anticipation of a threatening but formless event; a feeling of uneasy suspense. Additionally, anxiety is defined as distress or uneasiness of the mind caused by fear of danger or misfortune (Suleimenova, 2013).

According to Daud et al. (2019), speaking anxiety is the fear that is faced by students when delivering or preparing a speech in front of people or the public. Whether in front of a few people or a large crowd, people can still experience anxiety when speaking.

Speaking in English is also a big reason why students feel anxious when speaking in public. People who experience this anxiety may be unaware that they are suffering from Glossophobia, which is the fear of public speaking. Glossophobia has been derived from the Greek word glossa- meaning tongue, and -Phobos, fear (Milan, 2019).

Public speaking is something people do to give their thoughts and ideas to a large audience. However, according to Katz (2000), "Public speaking anxiety is very common among both college students and the general population. Some estimates are as many as 20-85% of people experience more or less anxiety when they need to speak in public." A lot of people experience anxiety when public speaking because of various factors and causes like lack of preparation or fear of negative evaluation. According to Wardhani (2019), students' unwillingness to participate in speaking activities in the classroom is caused by their assumption of being judged negatively and their lack of mastery of the speaking skill. Another definition given by the APA Dictionary of Psychology is the "Fear of giving a speech or presentation in public because of the expectation of being negatively evaluated or humiliated by others. This is a common fear, associated with social phobia." Although it may be a common fear, this can cause students, future working and functioning adults, trouble when speaking in public.

According to Eke (2021), once you are called upon to deliver a speech, there is the tendency that you will experience some anxiety in you. The ability to manage this anxiety is of paramount importance to a public speaker. Having the ability to manage your anxiety while delivering speech prevents a person from shaking, sweating, rapid heartbeat, having a squeaky voice, and stuttering.

According to Wang, et al. (2021), "High levels of anxiety may have a correlation with high levels of stress, which is more common in

those with a low socioeconomic status. Those with a lower socioeconomic status often receive lower quality resources, such as education.” This means that a person’s level of anxiety may be influenced by their socioeconomic status. It also suggests that a person who happens to be less fortunate has a higher likelihood of experiencing high levels of anxiety.

Causes of Public Speaking Anxiety

In the study of Hutabarat and Simanjuntak (2019), the causes of speaking anxiety vary from the limitation of English exposure to learning conditions. In the study of Lungay (2023), it was identified that Philippine university students' language elements, lack of grammatical understanding, pronunciation factor, stage fear, lack of confidence, shyness, and peer factor are the contributing factors. It was remarked that these factors were derived from Simanjuntak’s study.

Limitations of English Exposure

Having limited time is one of the sources that leads to the students feeling anxious when speaking in English. Meanwhile, to be a good English speaker, students must practice their speaking skills every day and practice a lot. Having limited outlet to English exposure, apparently, leads most of the students to feel anxiety when they speak English. To be sufficient in speaking English, students must have a lot of practice using the language; they must speak outside and inside the classroom effectively. According to Chand (2021), if learners do not get a chance to practice any language either in the classroom or out of the classroom then it becomes very difficult to learn a language.

Fear of Negative Evaluation

Fear of negative evaluation is identified as one of the themes that lead students to feel anxious when they speak in the English language (Horwitz, 1986; as cited in Liu & Jakson, 2008). Previous studies claimed that speaking anxiety is caused by many factors such as low perceived self-efficacy and fear of negative evaluation (Gkonou, 2011, as cited in Mestan, 2017). In addition, Sari et al. (2013) stated that “the embarrassment that students feel when they expose their language imperfections to others and the possibility of negative feedback from the 53 instructors increases anxiety levels significantly. The categories that emerged from this theme are difficulty using grammar, lack of vocabulary knowledge, and mispronunciation.”

Difficulty in Using Grammar

Using correct grammar is challenging for people. Meanwhile, the use of grammar is one of the most important elements in English especially when speaking English; the speakers must have sufficient knowledge of English grammar so that their interlocutors can comprehend what the speakers are saying (Purpura, 2004).

Lack of Vocabulary Knowledge

Vocabulary is an important component of the language teaching and learning process, and correct pronunciation of lexical items is a goal for English teachers or instructors who deal with English programs. Vocabulary is viewed as one of the important factors that make them feel anxious when they start speaking English in front of the class. According to Sari et al. (2013), one of the most important aspects of speaking is vocabulary mastery.

Pronunciation Errors

According to Aziz, et al. (2021), pronunciation is the most important aspect in communication. It is one of the ways the speaker produces language when they are talking with each other nicely. However, having proper pronunciation requires hard work. People claim that they tend to make errors in pronouncing English words (Hutabarat & Simanjuntak, 2019).

Learning Condition

The atmosphere of the classroom becomes one of the most important supports for students to learn every subject, including learning English. Comfortable, safe, and conducive classroom situations will help students enjoy learning. However, the sources that make the students uncomfortable to learn English are when the classrooms are not conducive, a disturbance can be imminent everywhere. In addition, a very noisy room will disturb the students’ concentration on learning (Hutabarat & Simanjuntak, 2019).

Strategies for Overcoming Public Speaking Anxiety

There are different strategies that can be used by students to cope with their anxiety in public speaking. According to Raja (2017), interception of teachers, preparation, seeking feedback, focusing on the speech material, and joining various speaking activities were the best remedies or strategies that can be used to eliminate speaking anxiety. On one hand, in the study of Maharani and Roslaini (2021), the strategies in overcoming public speaking anxiety were categorized into five such as preparation, positive thinking, relaxation, peer seeking, and resignation. Wherein, it was found out that preparation is the most used by students when they feel anxious about a speaking activity. Preparation is defined as preparing before a public speech, in this aspect the students would use various techniques to prepare themselves for delivering the speech. While positive thinking is more of the students’ way to calm themselves down or distract themselves from the pressure of anxiety. Another is Relaxation this could be the same as positive thinking as it is a form of a calming down method, but the difference is in this aspect the student would do something to feel at ease in public speaking.

This category involves action while for positive thinking, it confines the student in thoughts. As for Peer Seeking, the student asks for help from friends. They find this strategy as a form of comfort through their peers' words and thoughts. And lastly, for the Resignation the student would accept the situation and prefer it as a "it is what it is" thought. The student would not do anything else but rather in this category they would not prepare or do anything to the speech. This strategy makes it seem that the student does not care at all about their speech presentation and would not do anything if they accepted what would happen to them.

Despite numerous studies dealing with students' anxiety in public speaking, there is still a need to conduct this study since not much was conducted here in the Philippines. If ever there are studies that were conducted in the Philippines, they only focused on measuring the students' speech anxiety and did not seek to look for the variables that could have contributed to that anxiety level like as of Alora et al (2023). If there are studies that all seek to determine the variable that is attributed to the students' speech anxiety level, they do not consider socioeconomic status as a variable such as in the study of Lungay (2023). Another thing to consider why there is a need to study student speech anxiety in the Philippines is because the studies that are already conducted are focused on people who use English as a foreign language (EFL) unlike in the Philippines with students who use English as a second language (ESL). So, the results and findings may differ because it is conducted among students in Philippine ESL classrooms. In addition to that, this study is fundamental to students to develop their awareness regarding their level of speech anxiety and determine the causes of their speech anxiety. Furthermore, the students will also learn what strategies they could apply to overcome their anxiety. Aside from that, this study will also help the teachers in planning and designing their lessons that would further develop the communication skills of their students, especially in public speaking. Finally, it will also aid the teachers in creating or implementing strategies that could enhance the level of confidence and lessen or eliminate the speaking anxiety among their students.

The findings of the study will benefit various individuals such as students, teachers, and the administration and may help the students who experience high speaking anxiety and whose grades are affected due to their performances in public speaking such as recitation, reporting, acting or roleplays, and others. According to Christy et al. (2020), students who experience high levels of anxiety have low academic performance. This is in contrast to those who experience low anxiety levels and have a high academic performance. Another benefit that may be gained in this paper is that this paper may become a basis for forums, conferences, and symposiums, and other forms of talks about coping with those who experience public speaking anxiety.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the SHS Grade 11 students' Level of Anxiety in Public Speaking, its causes, and strategies. This paper intended to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' level of anxiety in public speaking?
2. What are the causes of anxiety in public speaking?
3. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' level of anxiety when they are grouped according to the following profile variables:
 - 3.1. sex;
 - 3.2. strand;
 - 3.3. type of junior high school attended; and
 - 3.4. socio-economic status?
4. What are the strategies of the students for overcoming anxiety in public speaking?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used both quantitative and qualitative research methods, particularly descriptive-comparative research design. For the descriptive design, this study described the level of anxiety in public speaking and the causes of anxiety in public speaking. It also analyzed the comparison between the level of anxiety in public speaking as regards the respondent's sex, strand, type of junior high school attended, and socio-economic status. Qualitative research design was also utilized in identifying strategies in overcoming anxiety in public speaking.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the Grade 11 SMUSHS students from the various strands who were enrolled in the school year 2023-2024.

Using convenience sampling, Table 1 indicates that 200 respondents participated in the study. The majority of the respondents were female with a number of 104 participants while 96 of the respondents were male. In terms of the strand, the majority of the respondents were from the STEM strand with 121, followed by HUMSS with 37 respondents, ABM with 26 respondents, and 16 respondents from TVL-ICT, TVL-HE, and AD. Meanwhile, for the profile type of junior high school attended, 44 respondents attended public schools and 156 attended private schools. As regards the respondents' socio-economic status, the majority of the respondents' status were from 21,914 to 43,828 with 47 participants.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Counts of the Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Profile Variables</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex		
Male	96	48.00%
Female	104	52.00%
Total	200	100%
Strand		
STEM	121	60.50%
HUMSS	37	18.50%
ABM	26	13.00%
TVL-AD	16	8.00%
Total	200	100%
School attended		
Public	44	22.00%
Private	156	78.00%
Total	200	100%
Socio-economic Status		
Less than 10,957	26	13%
10,957 to 21,914	44	22%
21,914 to 43,828	47	23.5%
43,828 to 76,669	28	14%
76,669 to 131,484	26	13%
131,484 to 219,140	13	6.5%
219,140 and above	16	8%
Total	200	100.00%

Instruments

This study used a questionnaire which consisted of four parts. The first part consisted of the demographic profile such as the sex, strand, type of junior high school attended, and socioeconomic status. The second part of the questionnaire consists of a tool used to measure the level of public speaking anxiety or PRPSA. The research adopted McCroskey's PRPSA or Personal Report on Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA). This scale is an "excellent measure for research which centers on public speaking anxiety but is an inadequate measure of the broader communication apprehension construct" (McCroskey, 1970). This part of the questionnaire had 34 questions or statements that determined the participants' level of anxiety. This study used the Likert scale to measure the student's level of anxiety through the use of McCroskey's PRPSA. The participants answered the statements or questions by checking the number that corresponds with their answers. (1) = strongly disagree, (2) = disagree, (3) = neutral, (4) = agree, and (5) = strongly agree. The third part consists of a checklist that determines the possible causes of their public speaking anxiety. In this part the student-researchers made use of the study of Hutabarat and Simanjuntak (2019) that tackles the causes of public speaking anxiety. The last part of the questionnaire included an open-ended question that would identify the strategies on how to overcome anxiety in public speaking.

Table 2. *Cronbach's Alpha Result of the Reliability Statistics*

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.783	.771	34

McCroskey's scale had a highly reliable Cronbach's alpha of .90. This survey that the researchers floated is validated and passed the reliability testing, scoring .783 for its Cronbach's alpha (α). Based on the results this means that the questionnaire is acceptable.

Procedure

The research design included the adoption of the questionnaire from James McCroskey's Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA). After the questionnaire was modified and done, the content validation of the redesigned questionnaire was completed and reviewed by the research adviser. The questionnaire contains questions and checklists to find out the respondents' demographic factors including their name, sex, strand, school they attended, and socio-economic status. It also includes a part that measures the participants' level of anxiety through a Likert Scale. A checklist is also included to find out the causes of public speaking anxiety. Lastly, a qualitative open-ended question was included that asks the respondents how they cope with public speaking anxiety. The questionnaire was then

validated by the research adviser and the coordinator. The researchers then obtained a letter of approval from the principal’s office to disseminate the modified questionnaire. The authorized written consent letter was then used to float and distribute the questionnaires to the participants. The researchers conducted a pilot test to find out the reliability of the questionnaire. Upon completion of all questionnaires, the data were collected and tabulated using Microsoft Excel. The tabulated data were interpreted through reliable testing in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The researchers reported the findings after a comprehensive assessment and these results are used in the last chapter of the study.

Data Analysis

To treat the data gathered, the following statistical tools were utilized:

For descriptive statistics, frequency and percentage was used to determine the demographic profile variables of the respondents, such as their sex, strand, type of junior high school attended, their family’s socio-economic status, and causes of their anxiety in public speaking.

To determine the PRPSA score, the following steps were applied:

Step 1. Add scores for items 1, 2, 3, 5, 9, 10, 13, 14, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, and 34

Step 2. Add the scores for items 4, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 15, 16, 17, 18, 24, and 26

Step 3. The formula used is:

$$PRPSA = 72 - (\text{Total from Step 2}) + (\text{Total from Step 1})$$

The score should be between 34 and 170. If the score is below 24 or above 170, a mistake has been made in computing the score.

To determine the level of speech anxiety of the respondents, their PRPSA scores were categorized according to the following scale shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Categories for the PRPSA Results and Mean Interpretation

Categories	PRPSA Result	Mean Interpretation
Low Level of anxiety	34-84	1.00-1.49
Moderately Low Level of Anxiety	85-92	1.50-2.49
Moderate Level of Anxiety	93-110	2.50-3.49
Moderately High Level of Anxiety	111-119	3.50-4.49
High Level of Anxiety	120-170	4.50-5.00

For inferential statistics, to determine whether there is a significant difference between the respondents' level of anxiety in public speaking when they are grouped according to sex and school they attended, an independent sample t-test was used, while a one-way ANOVA was utilized in determining the significant difference of the respondents' level of anxiety in public speaking when grouped according to their strand and socio-economic status.

Thematic analysis was used for the qualitative part of this study specifically in determining the strategies in how to overcome anxiety in public speaking.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the findings of the study of the student-researchers. Together with the analysis of the Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) results, the implications of the results are shown in this section.

Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA) results.

Table 4. The respondents’ level of anxiety in public speaking

	Levels of Anxiety	%	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
Personal Report on Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA) of SMU Grade 11 SHS students	Low Level of Anxiety	5.5	3.74	1.196	
	Moderately Low Level of Anxiety	8.5			
	Moderate Level of Anxiety	29.0			Moderately High Level of Anxiety
	Moderately High Level of Anxiety	20.5			
	High Level of Anxiety	36.5			

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Low Level of Anxiety), 1.50-2.49 (Moderately Low Level of Anxiety), 2.50-3.49 (Moderate Anxiety), 3.50-4.49 (Moderately High Level of Anxiety), 4.50-5.00 (High Level of Anxiety)

Table 4 shows the calculated mean of the students’ Level of Anxiety which was gathered and calculated using James McCroskey’s Public Report on Public Speech Anxiety (PRPSA). It is reported that the calculated mean is equivalent to the level of moderate high

anxiety (\bar{X} =3.74, SD =1.196). This assumes that Saint Mary’s University Senior High School Grade 11 students have a moderately high anxiety level towards public speaking. This means that students encounter various anxiety problems when doing speaking activities. This can be seen as a problem since public speaking can never be avoided, especially in subjects that require a lot of speaking activities such as Oral Communication. This moderate high level of anxiety may affect the respondents’ grades as well because of underperforming in tasks and activities like recitation and reporting. This problem in some reviewed cases came even before 11th grade and could even be carried out until the students go to college and get a job.

The study of Christy et al. (2020) states that “it can be assumed that a student will possibly perform well when he/she has low anxiety on each indicator of speaking anxiety. Moreover, students with too low and medium level of anxiety will probably perform well enough.” Additionally, in the study by Tiyas et al. (2019), it was stated that all students have practiced English public speaking, and some have started in middle school and high school. This means that even before 11th grade, students have already experienced anxiety in public speaking. Furthermore, in the study of Alora et al. (2023), it was identified that Grade 12 senior high students of Pulang Santol National High School had a moderate anxiety level towards public speaking. This means that students even at a higher grade level than the respondents of the study could be subjected to an anxiety level that is close to the one that the student-researchers had computed. The study by Gallego et al. (2022) found that there is a high level of speaking anxiety among college students, and a majority of these students had little to almost no speaking anxiety where they attended. This study supports the implication that students could even be more anxious as they grow older, like being in college and soon enough getting jobs, where perhaps this speech anxiety that they possess would take a toll on their jobs.

The respondents’ causes of anxiety

Table 5. The causes of anxiety in public speaking

Causes	Frequency	Percentage
Fear of Negative Evaluation	193	96.5%
Limitation of English Exposure	173	86.5%
Learning Condition	141	70.5%

Table 5 indicates the frequency and percentage of the causes of public speaking anxiety. The data indicates that among the causes of public speaking anxiety is the fear of negative evaluation (f =193, $percentage$ =96.5%). This indicates that most students have public speaking anxiety because of their fear of being judged by their peers, classmates, or teachers. This could mean that an audience, even if it consists of their peers and classmates, can make students anxious when participating in classes that involve public speaking. As the student may feel that their judgment may put on their mistakes during their speech. The leading statement that the participants with a total of 152 students agreed with is “I want to make my sentences correct before speaking”. This could mean that the students have a fear of making an error while doing a speaking activity. This, in turn, can mean that the students prepare or practice for the speaking activity as a solution to avoid errors. In regard to the leading statement, students could try to furnish their speeches before delivering them, but as anxiety would begin to trigger within the student, the practiced speech might not guarantee proper delivery, and various signs of shaking, sweating, rapid heartbeat, having a squeaky voice, and stuttering (Eke, 2021). Or the situation may be that practicing the speech itself may be the cause of anxiety for the student.

These findings resonate with the study of Daud, et al. (2019) where the various factors that affect students are fear of making mistakes, feeling under pressure, and fear of negative evaluation from the teacher. This suggests that despite numerous factors and causes, fear of negative evaluation is a big reason for the anxiety of students in public speaking. Negative evaluation may not only come from peers but also from other people like teachers and classmates/schoolmates. Students want to avoid mistakes because they have a fear of failing, explaining the choice of students to check the statement “I want to make my sentences correct before speaking” These findings are also parallel to another study by Downing et al. (2020) where fear of negative evaluation is the “primary construct underlying student anxiety in active learning in the community college science classroom”. This could imply that even outside of senior high school, up until college or even until adulthood, the fear of negative evaluation can be the prime reason for the individuals’ public speaking anxiety.

The Level of Anxiety in Public Speaking of Saint Mary’s University Senior High School students when grouped according to their profile variable.

Table 6. Comparison of the level of speech anxiety of the respondents when grouped according to sex

Groups	f (n=200)	Mean	SD	QD	t(197.060)	p-value
Male	96	3.63	1.10	Moderately High level of Anxiety	-1.317	0.037
Female	104	3.85	1.28	Moderately High level of Anxiety		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 6 presents the difference in the students’ level of anxiety and sex. It was identified using an independent t-test that there is a significant difference between the calculated PRPSA report of the students and their Sex. It shows that both sexes have the possibility of having anxiety, but female students (M =3.85, SD =1.275) are more likely to be affected by speech anxiety than their male

counterparts ($M=3.63$, $SD=1.098$); $t(197.060)=-1.317$, $p=0.037$. This implies that anxiety is likely to affect females more than males due to various circumstances such as brain functions and hormones within their bodies (Maeng et al). This means that in a classroom or at jobs that require their workers to do speeches, women are more likely to feel the effects of anxiety than their male counterparts.

The study of Bahrami and Yousefi (2011) states that anxiety thoughts affect girls more than boys; they have more metacognitive beliefs about the uncontrollability of worry and believe that worry must be avoided. This may imply that females have a higher level of anxiety because of their worries. These results contradict studies where there is no statistically significant difference between male and female levels of speaking anxiety like that of Fauziyah et al. (2022) conducted in Malaysia, an EFL country. This may mean that the environment or country in which the research has been conducted, whether it is EFL or ESL, may affect the level of anxiety of the students according to sex. Meanwhile, this contrasts the study of Lungay (2023) wherein it was found there is no significant difference between the students of Cagayan de Oro College when grouped according to sex. This may be the result of his study because of the unequal frequency of the male and female respondents. Whereas female respondents are more than the male, on the other hand, this may have a significant difference as a result because of the close to equal response between males and females.

Table 7. Comparison of the level of speech anxiety of the respondents when grouped according to Strand

Groups	f	Mean	SD	QD	F-Value	p-value
STEM	121	4.02	1.176	Moderately High Level of Anxiety		
HUMSS	37	3.24	1.140	Moderate Level of Anxiety		
ABM	26	3.15	1.255	Moderate Level of Anxiety		
TVL-AD	16	3.75	0.577	Moderately High Level of Anxiety	0.308	0.820

*Not Significant ($p>0.05$)

Table 7 discusses the difference in the Level of Anxiety of the students and their enrolled Strands. After running the data in the SPSS, it can be read that there is no significant difference between the students' Level of Anxiety and their enrolled Strands [$F(6)=0.308$, $p=0.820$]. Regardless of the strand, anyone can be subjected to a high level of anxiety towards public speaking. This means that even if the student is enrolled in a strand that focuses on speech activities such as HUMSS, the student can still be subjected to a possible high level of speaking anxiety.

In contrast to the study of Lungay (2023), it was stated that there is a significant difference between the students' strands when grouped according to their public speaking anxiety and their chosen academic tracks. It was noted in the study that students chose strands according to their capability or motivation for the strand, an instance of this are HUMSS students choosing the strand because of its focus on speech activities. However according to Taufik et al. (2023), some students chose senior high school strands because they are either undecided, parents choosing it for them, or because of their peers. The majority of the senior high school students in the Philippines right now face this kind of situation. In a study done by Malaguial et al. (2018), 73.86% of students chose the strand of STEM because of its many career opportunities, but a majority of the students enrolled in this strand are misplaced because most of their skills do not align at all with the strand. So, at times, the usage of senior high students as a form of research subject may not have a permanent result for various schools. After all, different students have a different mindset towards their academic tracks. Only a few students got into a track that is aligned with their skills and capabilities. This goes well in different schools that enact different teaching methods for their students in public speaking.

Table 8. Comparison of the level of speech anxiety of the respondents when grouped according to the School they attended

Groups	f	Mean	SD	QD	t (144)	p-value
Private	116	3.83	1.22	Moderately High Level of Anxiety	1.224	0.973
Public	84	4.13	1.22	Moderately High Level of Anxiety		

*Not Significant ($p>0.05$)

Table 8 shows the difference between the Level of Anxiety and the type of junior high attended. It was identified using an independent t-test that there is no significant difference between the calculated PRPSA report of the students upon whether they attended Private schools ($M=3.83$, $SD=1.218$) or Public schools ($M=4.13$, $SD=1.224$): [$t(144)=1.224$, $p=0.223$]. This meant there was no difference in where the students attended. Whether it be from a private school or a public school, their level of anxiety is unaffected by this factor.

In the study of Cadiz-Gabejan (2022), it was found that students with different school backgrounds have different capacities when learning grammar and as well as different speaking activities. Some students, especially at higher grade levels that would come from public schools would be more exemplary than those from private schools. But when it comes to speaking activities, the students from private schools, especially those at younger ages of 6 to 12 years old would excel better than those from public schools. But as the age range becomes older, the results are almost the same. This relates to the study as it could mean that educational attainment for each student does not vary whether they come from a public or private school. Meanwhile, the study by Vukosi et al. (2021) found that public or private schools had a massive role in shaping children's anxieties towards public speaking. Especially in the teachers that administer the activities in public speaking, their lack of control or encouragement towards the students in the classroom, whether private or public, is highly influential. This is crucial, especially at a young age when development is rampant. However, some students do not get any help at all because of the number of students one teacher needs to look after, instead, they aid this by self-taught

techniques that at times work and at times do not. However, the teachers' lack of control is not just the reason why every student can not be monitored. Instead, it is attributed to the high ratio of students against the small ratio of one teacher in each classroom.

Table 9. Comparison of the level of speech anxiety of the respondents when grouped according to Socioeconomic status

Groups	f	Mean	SD	DQ	F-Value	p-value
Less than 10,957	26	3.62	1.27	Moderately High Level of Anxiety	0.689	0.659
10,957-43,828	44	3.93	0.873	Moderately High Level of Anxiety		
21,914-43,828	47	3.79	1.141	Moderately High Level of Anxiety		
43,828-76,669	28	3.71	1.243	Moderately High Level of Anxiety		
76,669-131,484	26	3.35	1.441	Moderate Level of Anxiety		
131,484-219,140	13	4.31	0.95	Moderately High Level of Anxiety		
219,140 and above	16	3.50	1.55	Moderately High Level of Anxiety		

*Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Table 9 displays the difference between the socio-economic status of students and their level of anxiety. There is no statistically significant difference between groups as determined by one-way ANOVA [(F(6)=0.689, $p=0.659$)]. This means that the level of anxiety of the students has no difference whether they have a low or high socio-economic status. It furthers that even if students are born into a low-income family, they have an equal chance to experience speech anxiety, this also goes with high-income families. Perhaps this is the result because speech anxiety is somewhat not impacted by the socioeconomic status of an individual.

In a similar study done by Lungay (2023), it was found that there is no significant difference between the students of Cagayan de Oro College when grouped according to their Family's socioeconomic status. This might be so because everyone can be affected by speech anxiety, even those who are born into a family that earns very well can also be affected by anxiety, as anxiety does not pick those who may be affected. Rather, everyone already can feel a certain type of anxiety when performing, but not everyone can experience high levels.

Meanwhile, the study of Lungay (2023) and as well as what was found in the study goes against the study of Baroi et al. (2020) where there are significant differences in foreign language in foreign language speaking anxiety among different levels of a residential area, socio-economic status, parental education, and father's occupation. As well as in the study by Kumar et al. (2017) there exists a significant difference in public speaking anxiety among students from different socioeconomic levels. These studies were conducted in Bangladesh, an EFL country, and India, which is an ESL country, respectively. This may mean that the students in the Philippines do not regard socio-economic status as a problem or driver of public speaking anxiety, despite the country being also an ESL country. It can be said that a person's ability to learn and acquire public speaking skills may not be affected by how rich or poor he or she is, thus affecting their level of public speaking anxiety.

The strategies of the students to overcome their anxieties in public speaking.

Table 10. Thematic analysis of the coping strategies of students with speech anxiety (n=200)

Strategies	Responses	n	%
Preparation	1. For me, I just follow the steps in public speaking. I follow what, when, where, and why, commonly I follow this guidelines and when I'm speaking in public, I always talk slowly and clearly. As long as I can transmit the message or point of what I'm saying. And first of all, we should know what we're talking about because it's the main foundation when we are in public.	96	48
	2. I practice in front of the mirror to both prepare my speech and to remove my unease.		
	3. The strategies I do sometimes to help with my anxiety in public speaking is by rehearsing on my spare time the day before the speaking and building confidence from it.		
Positive Thinking	1. o overcome anxiety in public speaking I think of things that help me overcome by always thinking positive and clarity in better persons to communicate.	48	24
	2. I just focus on myself and not think about the things that make me anxious.		
	3. I always value the satisfaction of being able to entertain people, even just a few.		
Relaxation	1. Breath control, it helps me to calm down.	23	11.5
	2. Breathe in breathe out, I try to relax myself or play ballpen or anything I am holding so I can calm myself		
	3. Breathing exercise, calming myself down through distractions in my environment, making myself believe that things will be okay, and many more.		
Resignation	1. Picturing no one is there	36	18
	2. It depends but I think its just a matter of getting used to it. Another one is I try my best to gaslight myself that I am the only one talking in the room and no one else.		
	3. I don't know and until now I don't know what to do do to avoid anxiety in public speaking.		
Peer Seeking	1. I practice my speech in front of my friends to eliminate anxiety.	7	3.5
	2. To overcome anxiety in public speaking, you can practice social skills by practicing conversations, public speaking, and other social interactions.		
	3. I practice more in front of my friends as my audience and also by doing strategies ou teacher gave. And exposing myself in front of many people through dancing to gain confidence.		

Table 10 student-researchers thematic analysis, it was identified that the category of Preparation had the highest frequency and percentage counting to its ($f=96$, Percentage of 48%). This means that Preparation is the most used coping strategy in combating their anxiety in public speaking. As they may have time to polish up their speeches or prepare themselves before presenting their speeches.

Students who prepare before a public speaking activity are more likely to feel less anxious about their speech than those who do not prepare at all. In the study of Raja (2017), people who have better preparation and understanding of the topic before doing a speech are likely to have better performance on the subject. It allows the speaker to fix what is needed to be fixed within themselves and enhance what is needed to be enhanced in their speaking activities. According to Juneja (2015), public speaking is never an easy task. One needs to practice in a rigorous process for anxiety to ease down or at least be controlled by the speaker. By then, proper delivery of a speech can be ensured. In addition to this, Smith and Frymier (2006) says that consistent practice can help one become more accustomed to giving speeches and the environment of public speaking in general. This might encourage better self-control and more effective speech presentations.

Conclusion

Anxiety remains to be one of the most talked about topics in today's society. Many saw the need to talk about it as it is now a prevailing topic to many, especially in terms of speech in anxiety. This is an important topic, especially for students where speech activities cannot be avoided. The following conclusions were derived based on the results and findings:

The findings of the study found that the senior high school students had a moderate-high anxiety level. This meant that the students had already a close to a high level of speaking anxiety, this can be alarming considering that, speaking activities can not be avoided at an academic level, especially in subjects that emphasize activities on public speaking such as Oral Communication.

Furthermore, the fear of negative evaluation is the most prevalent reason why students feel anxious about public speaking. Anxiety when speaking stems from excessive fears of performance situations where there is a chance of receiving negative feedback from others.

Public speaking anxiety should not be a hindrance to everyone. Although one's sex was identified to have a significant difference with one's level of anxiety, because of biological factors such as in the brain and hormones. But one should not use it as a hindrance to not feel anxious about public speaking. On the other hand, the study's socio-economic status, the school they attended, and as strand do not have any difference in their level of anxiety towards public speaking. This concludes that one's background does not affect their level of anxiety toward public speaking.

Moreover, various mechanism strategies were also identified. As many as there were, it was found that practice is still the most effective among all identified coping strategies. The concept of preparation prepares the students in how they compose themselves, their speeches, and as well as how their speeches will be delivered. Thus, it is necessary to look for proper preparation techniques to properly prevent speech anxiety during a performance.

Based on the findings and conclusion, this study recommends that teachers would be more inclined to prepare students for public speaking activities to better see that they may handle the task. Guidance is a necessity in proper preparation for tasks like public speaking activities. But if the situation escalates, and it becomes uncontrollable to an extent where the student becomes unable to speak even just a word, reaching out to a professional such as a counselor, psychiatrist, or speech therapist is highly advisable. Another is to encourage the students to try more preparatory styles, whether self-preparatory or with the guidance of a peer. It could be also in the form of reading a speech and trying to visualize one presenting a speech.

For future researchers, it is recommended to conduct a study to determine if there are differences in anxiety levels among these variables gender, family upbringing, Mother Tongue at home, MBTI (Myer-Briggs Type Indicator), club affiliation, and grade level.

Future researchers can use the gender variable to remove the limit on the variable sex. Gender could be a reason for a person's ability to speak well in public. In addition, the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) could be another variable to consider that could affect the level of anxiety of students. Examining whether being an introvert has a bigger impact on anxiety when speaking in public, or if being an extrovert equates to less anxiety when speaking. As for family upbringing, future student-researchers should look into the effects of how the environment that they grew up in could eventually affect their ability to speak publicly, such of these are those who grew up in an extended family, nuclear, and other forms. On the other hand, Mother Tongue could attribute to how a person might feel less anxious in their own language when speaking their own language or dialect rather than the English language where they might feel anxious. This can be compared with how anxious day feel speaking in the English language. Additionally, future researchers could investigate the potential effect of being a member of a certain club or organization on anxiety levels. Being a member of different organizations and clubs, inside or outside the school, or not can be a determining factor for students' level of anxiety. Furthermore, expand the scope of respondents from Grade 11 to include the entire senior high school population, which could have an impact on the results of the study.

For teachers, more collaboration in preparing the students for public speaking activities to better see that they may handle the task. Guidance is a necessity in proper preparation for tasks like public speaking activities. But if the situation escalates, and it becomes

uncontrollable to an extent where the student becomes unable to speak even just a word, reaching out to a professional such as a counselor, psychiatrist, or speech therapist is highly advisable. Another is to encourage the students to try more preparatory styles, whether self-preparatory or with the guidance of a peer. It could be also in the form of reading a speech and trying to visualize one presenting a speech.

For the curriculum plans, it is recommended to evaluate, review, and if possible, revise the existing plans to widen the scope of the lessons especially in Oral Communication that will further improve the communicative competence of the students, as well as to tackle the anxiety problems of students in public speaking. This can be through the inclusion of lessons that can help in reducing their anxiety in public speaking. These lessons can include strategies on overcoming public speaking anxiety such as different forms of preparation, relaxation, and positive-thinking.

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